

IMPACT OF SELF HELP GROUP TOWARDS WOMEN EMPOWERMENT

Mrs.R.Sheela Devi

Assistant professor, Nehru Arts and Science College, Coimbatore.

Dr. M. Gowrisankar

Dean & Associate Professor, Sree Ramu College of Arts and Science, Pollachi.

ABSTRACT

The study examines the impact of Self-Help Groups (SHGs) on women empowerment, focusing on the ways these groups promote economic independence, social mobility, and decision-making capabilities among women. Self-Help Groups have emerged as a powerful tool for collective action, allowing women from various socio-economic backgrounds to come together, share resources, and develop entrepreneurial skills. This research explores the multifaceted empowerment that SHGs foster, including enhanced financial literacy, access to credit, and improved income generation. Additionally, SHGs facilitate social empowerment by creating a support network that strengthens women's confidence, assertiveness, and leadership within their communities. Data was collected from various SHGs across rural and urban regions to assess the changes in participants' income, education, healthcare access, and overall autonomy. The findings indicate that SHGs significantly contribute to women's empowerment by promoting financial stability, boosting self-esteem, and fostering collective social awareness. This research underscores the potential of SHGs to be instrumental in addressing gender inequality and providing a sustainable framework for women's socio-economic progress. The study advocates for increased support for SHGs to further their impact in achieving holistic empowerment for women.

KEYWORDS

Self Help Groups, Women Empowerment Skill Development, Increased Confidence, Social Support,

INTRODUCTION

SHG is a form of micro-level financial institution where poor women join together to manage their future and their economic upliftment. Some of these groups have been formed in different countries and have play a great role of empowering women and campaigning for gender equality. The basis for forming the SHGs is that women assist fellow women in attaining their desired objectives in order to better their standards of living. As partners in SHGs women are able to share finances and be in a position to access microfinance, education, and be empowered through structured training and decision making. SHGs have been mostly discussed here in regard to empowering women and actually success has been reported to be improving in financial aspects, skill development, confidence, health and literacy levels. In this article, a critical exploration of the degree of empowering of women through SHGs and reasons for this will be explored.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Women around the world face numerous challenges and obstacles in their daily lives, including poverty, lack of education and job opportunities, lack of access to financial resources, and limited political representation. These challenges prevent women from achieving their full potential and participating in society on an equal footing with men. Despite progress in some areas, gender inequality remains a persistent problem that affects women in all aspects of life. The goal of the problem statement is to comprehend how Self Help Groups (SHGs) affect women's empowerment and how they support women's rights and the eradication of gender inequality. Studying how SHGs benefit women's lives makes it possible to create plans for expanding and replicating their effectiveness in other areas.

OBJECTIVES

- To find out personal profile of the respondents.
- To examine the impact of Self Help Groups (SHGs) on women's empowerment.
- To discuss the reasons behind the success of SHGs in empowering women and promoting gender equality.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

"The role of Self-Help Groups in Empowering Rural Women: A Study of Tamil Nadu, India" (Chitra, 2017)–In this study, the effect of SHGs on women's empowerment in rural Tamil Nadu, India, is examined. The results demonstrate how SHGs have aided women in raising

their social standing in their communities, increasing their ability to make decisions, and improving their financial situation.

"The Impact of Self-Help Groups on Women's Empowerment in Nigeria" (**Nwosu, 2016**) - In this study, the effect of SHGs on women's emancipation in Nigeria is assessed. According to the study, SHGs have helped women become more financially independent, enhance their health and education, and boost their political representation.

"The Effect of Self-Help Group Participation on Women's Empowerment in Bangladesh" (**Hossain, 2018**)—The impact of SHGs on women's emancipation in Bangladesh is examined in this study. The results demonstrate that SHGs have boosted women's social support, confidence, and self-esteem, as well as their financial situation.

"The Role of Self-Help Groups in Women's Empowerment in Uganda" (**Nakitende, 2019**) - The impact of SHGs on women's emancipation in Uganda is examined in this study. The results demonstrate that SHGs have helped women become more financially independent, enhance their health and education, and expand their political representation.

"Women's Empowerment through Self-Help Group Participation in South Africa" (**Ndlovu, 2018**) - This paper evaluates the impact of SHGs on women's empowerment in South Africa. The study found that SHGs have contributed to increased financial independence, improved health and education, and enhanced social status for women.

Impact of Self Help Groups towards Women Empowerment

Self Help Groups (SHGs) are a grassroots level organization of women who come together to support each other for their economic and social well-being. These group have been active in fighting for woman rights and advocating for women rights in all aspects. The subject of this article is the influence of self-help groups on women's status and indispensability of these groups will be explained.

- **Financial Independence:** Self Help Groups empower women with micro finance as a tool of starting and expanding their own ventures. This financial liberation has helped empower women and at the same time helped them let go of some of the strings they held on to when it comes to men.

- **Skill Development:** SHGs allow women to gain new skills and therefore improve their standard of living. It offers education in other fields like managerial, financial, and leadership skills making women stand on their own.
- **Increased Confidence:** By engaging the women in SHGs the chance to lead and produce group tasks can encourage more confidence and self-esteem in women. It has a positive spin to their personal and professional development and enables the members take on more leadership responsibilities in their society.
- **Social Support:** Women in SHGs have a support system in place, which helps them to cope with life's challenges. They are able to share their experiences, problems and provide each other with emotional support, which is crucial for their overall well-being.
- **Improved Health:** Women in SHGs have access to health services and information, which helps to improve their health and reduce their vulnerability to diseases. This has a positive impact on their overall quality of life and their ability to contribute to their communities.
- **Improved Education:** Women in SHGs are encouraged to educate themselves and their children, which leads to improved educational outcomes. This has a positive impact on their future economic opportunities and their ability to contribute to their communities.
- **Political Empowerment:** Women in SHGs are given the opportunity to participate in local decision-making processes, which helps to increase their political voice and representation. This has a positive impact on the overall empowerment of women in their communities.
- **Improved Status within Households:** Women in SHGs are able to improve their status within their households by becoming more financially independent and decision-makers. This has a positive impact on their overall well-being and the well-being of their families.
- **Increased Political Representation:** Women in SHGs are able to increase their political representation by participating in local decision-making processes and by advocating for their rights.
- **Improved Economic Opportunities:** Women in SHGs are able to improve their economic opportunities through

METHODOLOGY:

Study Area:

SHG members' socioeconomic circumstances and other relevant factors were gathered through the researcher's planned questionnaire routine. Two hundred SHG members were chosen from among the several self-help groups in the Coimbatore District to participate in the study that was performed for this reason.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. AGE OF THE MEMBERS OF SELF HELP GROUP

Age factor	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Below 30 years	56	29
31 – 40 years	75	38
Above 40 years	69	34
Total	200	100

Out of the total respondents included for the research, 28% are under 30, 38% are between 31 and 40, and the remaining 34% are above 40, according to the statistics above. The bulk of responders were found to be between the ages of 31 and 40.

2. EDUCATIONAL QUALIFICATION OF THE MEMBERS

Educational Qualification	No of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Illiterate	46	22
Literate	152	78
Total	200	100

The Table reveals the literacy rates of the Self Help Group members, with 78% of them being literate and the remaining 22% being illiterate. The majority of respondents about 78% of all were found to be literate.

3. PERSONAL ASPECTS CHANGE BEING INVOLVED IN SHGS

Changes observed on personal	High level	Moderate level
Rise in social status	75 (49)	77 (51)
Ability to work together with outsiders	73 (47)	79 (53)
Participation in deciding children's education	96 (63)	56 (37)
Access to sanitation facility	39 (26)	113 (74)
Ability to accept challenges	51 (34)	101 (66)
Deterioration in family	72 (47)	80 (53)
Ability to take inventive decision	70 (46)	82 (54)

The preceding Table shows that a significant portion of women see significant changes in their level of confidence with regard to taking part in decisions regarding their children's education and health as well as leaving their homes. The respondents reported modest levels of change for the following variables: an increase in social status, the capacity to interact with others, access to sanitary facilities, the capacity to handle difficulties, the capacity to handle family conflicts, the capacity to use family planning methods, the capacity to make creative decisions, and the capacity to support non-members in the face of cruelty and anti-women social norms. The fact that the women have joined other social organisations and are now aware of a variety of socio-political concerns is also disclosed.

SUGGESTIONS

Enhance Financial Literacy: Provide regular training on budgeting, savings, and financial management to help women manage funds effectively and increase their economic independence.

Increase Access to Credit and Resources: Facilitate easier access to micro-loans, grants, and government schemes to enable SHG members to start or expand income-generating activities.

Promote Skill Development and Vocational Training: Offer training in skills such as tailoring, handicrafts, agriculture, or digital literacy to broaden economic opportunities and increase employability.

Encourage Leadership and Decision-Making Roles: Organize workshops on leadership and decision-making to build confidence and encourage women to take active roles in family and community decisions.

Strengthen Community Support Networks: Create platforms for SHGs to interact and collaborate with other community groups, fostering a support network that enhances solidarity and mutual growth.

Enhance Digital Literacy: Equip women with basic digital skills, enabling them to access information, expand market reach for products, and manage finances through digital platforms.

Promote Health and Wellness Awareness: Integrate health education programs on nutrition, hygiene, and reproductive health to improve the overall well-being of women and their families.

Foster Legal Awareness and Rights Education: Provide knowledge about legal rights, inheritance laws, and anti-violence resources to empower women to protect their rights and combat discrimination.

Encourage Political Participation: Support SHG members in engaging with local governance by training them on civic rights and encouraging participation in village councils or local decision-making bodies.

Monitor and Measure Impact Regularly: Implement mechanisms to assess the impact of SHG activities on women's empowerment, which can guide improvements and showcase successful outcomes to attract further support and funding.

CONCLUSION:

The study demonstrates that becoming a member of a SHG is not simply about obtaining credit; rather, it is about a process of empowerment that results in the women becoming more independent on the social and economic fronts. Empowerment is the capacity to take control of one's life; it cannot be altered or delivered; it must be self-generated.

In field interaction, it was observed that few government officials do not scrutinize or assess the work of the NGOs. One of the major demotivating factors in the effective running of organizations is negligence of the government officials. Some organizations are formed to receive these subsidies from the SGSY, and when they are received, the members no longer look at the sustainability aspect of the plan. Moreover, it is also clear that most of the group members do not have the operational and administrative skills needed to manage the operation. Sometimes, stagnation concerns skill development and results and appears to stem from no collateral support, including instructions on how to start an activity. The study has established that SHG activities have offered the women a new set of opportunities and the situation is improving in the study area despite the level of lack or impediments that are still observed in actualizing the targeted level of result. In the choice of the beneficiaries to sustain the motivation in different spectrums of activities, efforts from the representatives of the State and society are required. When the locations for orientation and training, as well as advertisement of the products, is not well established in these desirable markets, the people's psychological egoisms are often subdued. Individual effectiveness is achieved according to the set threshold only after positive results on the personal level, and passion for group endeavors.

REFERENCE

1. Bhattacharya, D., &Kabeer, N. (2001). Gender, Collective Action and Property Rights: Evidence from West Bengal and Bangladesh. *Development and Change*, 32(1), 123-157.
2. Chimtengo, C. (2016). The Impact of Self-Help Groups on Women's Empowerment in Malawi. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research*, 6(9), 125-134.
3. Chitra, S. (2017). The role of Self-Help Groups in Empowering Rural Women: A Study of Tamil Nadu, India. *International Journal of Rural Management*, 13(2), 162-174.
4. Das, J., &Österling, M. (1999). Women's Empowerment and Economic Development. *Journal of International Affairs*, 53(1), 41-63.
5. Gupta, A. (2015). Self-Help Groups and Women's Empowerment: A Study of Women in Rural India. *Gender, Technology and Development*, 19(2), 153-169.
6. Hossain, M. (2018). The Effect of Self-Help Group Participation on Women's Empowerment in Bangladesh. *Social Science Research Network*, 1-12.

7. Kabeer, N. (1999). Resources, Agency, Achievements: Reflections on the Measurement of Women's Empowerment. *Development and Change*, 30(3), 435-464.
8. Kabeer, N. (2001). Conflicts over Credit: Re-evaluating the Empowerment Potential of Loans to Women in Rural Bangladesh. *World Development*, 29(2), 63-84.
9. Krishnaraj, M. (1996). *Women's Empowerment and Development*. Sage Publications.
10. Moghadam, V. M. (2005). Globalization, Gender, and the Rise of "Feminized" Labor. *Social Politics*, 12(3), 474-493.
11. Molyneux, M. (1985). Mobilization without Emancipation? Women's Interests, State and Revolution in Nicaragua. *Feminist Studies*, 11(2), 227-254.
12. Nakitende, J. (2019). The Role of Self-Help Groups in Women's Empowerment in Uganda. *Journal of African Studies and Development*, 11(3), 108-115.
13. Ndlovu, N. (2018). Women's Empowerment through Self-Help Group Participation in South Africa. *Social Science Research Network*, 1-12.
14. Njoroge, W. (2017). The Effect of Self-Help Groups on Women's Empowerment in Kenya. *Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research*, 7(5), 19-26.
15. Nwosu, C. (2016). The Impact of Self-Help Groups on Women's Empowerment in Nigeria. *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science Research*, 6(2), 83-92.
16. Patel, R. (2002). Microfinance and Women's Empowerment: The Indian Experience. *World Development*, 30(5), 833-846.
17. Rao, V. (2013). Women's Empowerment through Self-Help Groups in Rural India. *Economic and Political Weekly*, 48(19), 69-75.
18. Ravindra, J. (2014). Women's Empowerment through Self-Help Group Participation in Rural India. *Indian Journal of Gender Studies*, 21(3), 365-378.